

Missing-institutions in OpenAlex: Possible reasons, impact and solutions of data deficiency

Zhe Cao¹, Lin Zhang², Yuanyuan Shang³, Ying Huang⁴

¹ caozhe@whu.edu.cn

Center for Science, Technology & Education Assessment (CSTEA), Wuhan University, Wuhan (China)
School of Information Management, Wuhan University, Wuhan (China)

² linzhang1117@whu.edu.cn, ⁴ ying.huang@whu.edu.cn

Center for Science, Technology & Education Assessment (CSTEA), Wuhan University, Wuhan (China)
School of Information Management, Wuhan University, Wuhan (China)

Centre for R&D Monitoring (ECOOM) and Department of MSI, KU Leuven, Leuven (Belgium)

³ shangafra@163.com

Chinese Academy of Social Sciences Evaluation Studies, Beijing (China)

Abstract

The advent of open science calls for open data platforms with high data quality. As a fully open catalog of the global research system launched in January 2022, OpenAlex is faced with a severe data problem of missing-institutions. This study investigates the phenomenon of missing-institutions among journal articles in OpenAlex, and defines three types of institutional information – full institutional information (FII), partially missing institutional information (PMII) and completely missing institutional information (CMII). Our results show that the problem of missing-institutions exists in more than 60% of journal articles in OpenAlex, which is more severe among articles published in the early years or in Art and History. Based on sub-samples of the data, we further explore the possible solutions to complete the institutional information and summarize the causes of the missing-institutions. To highlight the potential risk of distorting the research results by using the missing-institution data, a case study focusing on a published research article is conducted. The underlying reasons for missing-institutions and the ways to cope with the problem for both users and the whole academic community are discussed at last. Our study may provide some enlightenment for the academia on the use of open resources.

Introduction

As the need to make the scientific process more transparent, inclusive and democratic grows stronger and stronger, “open science” has been gradually embraced by science policy circles (Mirowski, 2018). An open approach has been acknowledged as the best way to maximize the benefits of research for both scientists and the public (Boulton, 2012). Not only the scientific research can be accelerated, but also the public can be assured that funding for science, arising from their taxes, has been used responsibly (Woelfle, Olliaro, & Todd, 2011). Open scientific knowledge is one of the four key pillars of open science, which refers to open access to resources such as scientific publications, research data and metadata that are available in the public domain or under copyright (UNESCO, 2021). The open data platform are where abundant resources are housed and presented, playing a crucial role in the realization of open scientific knowledge. Growing willingness to be open in science is spawning more high-quality open data platforms.

On January 3rd in 2022, OpenAlex (<https://openalex.org/>), a fully open platform integrating multiple data sources including Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG), ORCID, Crossref, Unpaywall, etc., was launched. By now, the platform has been widely applied to the research on science of science (AlShebli, Rahwan, & Woon, 2018; Li et al., 2022; Tang, Li, & Ma, 2022; Wang et al., 2022; Zhao, Bu, & Li, 2021). It should be noted that, since OpenAlex is a replacement for MAG, a heterogeneous graph established in 2015 and retired in 2021, and has drawn all data from it, the studies based on OpenAlex include those based on MAG in our study. Specifically, OpenAlex features two main advantages:

- As a free alternative, OpenAlex is more accessible than subscription-based databases such as Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus. With the growing trend toward open science, the emergence of this platform is crucial in promoting academic communication and bridging the digital, technological and intellectual gaps that exist among or within countries and geographies.
- As an integration of data sources, OpenAlex has a huge data volume, outlining a knowledge map among *works*, *authors*, *venues*, *institutions* and *concepts* based on more than 200 million publications (Priem, Piwowar, & Orr, 2022). Its coverage has been proved broader than some traditional bibliometric databases like WoS (Scheidsteger & Haunschild, 2022; Scheidsteger et al., 2018). Euan Adie, the founder of Overton, a platform that tracks the research cited in policy documents, confirmed that Overton had been getting its data from various sources but has now switched to using only OpenAlex (Chawla, 2022).

Despite of the remarkable superiority of this platform, the phenomenon of missing-institutions is commonplace in OpenAlex, which has been noticed in a previous study but has not obtained an effective solution yet (Li et al., 2022). Usually, there are two important questions to consider when it comes to data quality issues – the coverage and the accuracy. Missing-institutions is a specific manifestation of data problems which describes the phenomenon of the lack of institutional information in a set of publications. In fact, institutional information is a kind of basic data in bibliometric research. As meso-level data, it can be linked to individuals at the micro-level, supporting studies on topics such as geographic mobility of researchers. It can also be linked to countries at the macro-level, supporting studies on topics such as cross-country comparisons and international collaboration. At the same time, institutional information itself is a research focus as well, with related studies covering topics like institutional efficiency (Wolszczak-Derlacz & Parteka, 2011), institutional ranking (Molinari & Molinari, 2008), institutional collaboration (Han et al., 2014), etc. Thereby, missing-institutions can be regarded as a case of data quality issues that is worthy of looking into.

Given the growing popularity of OpenAlex and the great importance of institutional information, this study intends to use OpenAlex as a representative of open data platforms and investigate the phenomenon of missing-institutions which is a serious problem of data quality.

To be more specific, we aim to answer the following three questions:

- (1) To what extent can the phenomenon of missing-institutions be observed in OpenAlex?
- (2) Are there possible solutions to complete the missing-institution data from users' perspective?
- (3) How may the missing-institution data distort the results of empirical studies?

On this basis, reasons causing missing-institutions, suggestions for users and possible solutions to the missing-institution problem will be discussed, in the hope that our study may provide some enlightenment on the better use of open resources for the academia. The research framework of our study is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research framework

Data and method

In OpenAlex, *works* are scholarly documents like *journal articles*, *books*, *datasets*, and *theses*, among which *journal article* is the focus of our study. Our analysis focuses on the institutional information in journal articles. As shown in Figure 2, each work has one or several authorships, and each authorship has one or several institutions, which is described by five labels – *id*, *display_name*, *ror*, *country_code* and *type*. It should be noted that different from the way of information organization in some more widely used databases like WoS and Scopus, the works in OpenAlex do not have a separate label containing the institution list, so we can only access to institutional information in journal articles through the data chain of “*works-authorships-institutions*”.

Figure 2. Five entities¹ in OpenAlex and institutional information in works

¹ When we downloaded data, the official statement was that OpenAlex linked five entities. However, the web that OpenAlex establishes is extending to more kinds of entities. In our study, we just keep consistent with the status when we retrieved data.

According to the five labels of institutions in journal articles, the labeling of the institutional information can be divided into the following three types:

- Full institutional information (FII)

For a piece of institutional information, all five labels are complete, which should be like:

```
{
  "id": "https://openalex.org/I45129253",
  "display_name": "University College London",
  "ror": "https://ror.org/02jx3x895",
  "country_code": "GB",
  "type": "education"
}
```

- Partially missing institutional information (PMII)

For a piece of institutional information, at least one but less than five labels are empty. Usually, the *display_name* is given, and other four labels are not. This type should be like:

```
{
  "id": null,
  "display_name": "Patient-Led Research Collaborative.",
  "ror": null,
  "country_code": null,
  "type": null
}
```

- Completely missing institutional information (CMII)

For a piece of institutional information, all five labels are empty, which should be like:

```
{
  "id": null,
  "display_name": null,
  "ror": null,
  "country_code": null,
  "type": null
}
or {}
```

In this way, each journal article should be either with all FII or with missing-institutions. Among articles with missing-institutions, both PMII and CMII may exist in the institutional information types.

When it comes to methods, this study is developed with mixed methods of descriptive statistics, manual matching and case study, based on a full database sample and specified sub-samples. Firstly, the descriptive statistics method is used to reveal the distribution of the journal articles with missing-institutions. Secondly, based on sub-samples, the causes of missing-institutions and the solutions to the data completion are investigated with the manual matching method. Finally, a case study based on an article published in a top journal which uses MAG as the data source is conducted, aiming to highlight the potential risks of distorting the research results when using missing-institution data, by comparing the results before and after the completion of institutional information.

Results

Prevalence of missing-institutions in OpenAlex

Based on OpenAlex full repository data, which has been updated to October 10, 2022 in our study, 121,872,819 journal articles (about 50% of all types of works in OpenAlex) contain 247,994,117 pieces of institutional information in total. According to whether all pieces of institutional information in an article are full, these articles can be classified into two categories – articles with FII (38.43%) and articles with missing-institutions (61.57%).² The severity of the missing-institution problem in OpenAlex can be clearly shown.

However, the prevalence of missing-institutions varies from year to year. As observed in the subplot on the left in Figure 3, as time goes by, the proportion of articles with FII has generally risen up, with the growth in 1980s and 2000s most prominent. Missing-institutions also happens to different extent across different research fields. 19 root-level *concepts* in OpenAlex are used here to represent different research fields. It should be noted that since an article can be labeled with more than one concept, the sum of articles in each concept is more than 121,872,819. It can be learned from the subplot on the right that missing-institutions is more common in journal articles in Art and History, whereas articles with FII occupy a relatively larger share of approximately 50% in Biology, Chemistry, Material science and Mathematics. Time-series changes in different research fields have been further compared, with no obvious difference observed. However, the proportion of articles with FII has generally increased earlier and more step by step among fields in natural sciences and life sciences. There was even a little peak around 1930s in fields such as Biology, Chemistry, Physics and Medicine.

Figure 3. Distribution of journal articles with missing-institutions across years and concepts

Since data regulations of different publishers and different journals differ from each other, the distribution of articles with missing-institutions across publishers and journals is further analyzed, as shown in Figure 4.

² We have also analysed the phenomenon of missing-institutions in authorships. 121,872,819 journal articles cover 366,851,172 authors in total, among whom about 47% have missing-institutions. In particular, 112,510,937 first authors are identified, among whom about 53% have missing-institutions. It can be learned that the data deficiency problem is prominent in authorships as well. However, since our major focus is missing-institutions at the paper level, further discussion at the author level is not included in this study.

Among the 10 most productive publishers, articles published by Cambridge University Press and Ovid Technologies (Wolters Kluwer) - Lippincott Williams & Wilkins suffer from missing-institutions more seriously, whereas those published by Elsevier, Springer Nature and Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers are the opposite. Considering the features of these publishers, we may find that those focusing on social sciences and humanities like SAGE and Taylor & Francis, and those of non-commercial types like Cambridge University Press and Oxford University Press, are more likely to have a lower percentage of articles with FII.

Among the 15 most productive journals that have articles published in 2022, the completeness of institutional information among articles published in *Social Science Research Network*, *PLOS ONE*, *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, *Blood* and *Scientific Reports* is relatively better, with 57.9%, 64.9%, 61.2%, 58.1% and 67.5% of articles with FII respectively. However, articles published in *The Lancet*, *BMJ*, *Notes and Queries* and *JAMA* have a larger proportion of missing-institutions, where the percentages of articles with FII are all lower than 12%. Notably, almost all articles published in *Reactions Weekly* and *Chemical & Engineering News* are with missing-institutions.

Note: the numbers in the labels denote the amount of journal articles of the corresponding type.

Figure 4. Distribution of journal articles with missing-institutions among Top 10 productive publishers and Top 15 productive journals

In brief, missing-institutions is prevalent in journal articles in OpenAlex, especially in articles published in earlier years and in the fields of Art and History. The phenomenon exists to varying

degrees across different publishers and journals as well, the reasons of which remain to be explored further.

Causes and solutions for missing-institutions

In this section, we explore the possible ways of completing institutional information based on a subsample, and investigate into the reasons for PMII and CMII during this process. We downloaded all journal articles published on August 1st in 2021, with a total number of 99,835, among which there are 17,311 articles (17.3%) with PMII and 24,237 articles (24.3%) with CMII. One hundred articles are randomly drawn from each of the two sets as samples. It should be noted that the publication date was selected randomly, and data was retrieved on October 23, 2022.

Analysis for PMII

Among 100 articles with PMII, 272 pieces of institutional information with empty labels are recognized. Since *display_name* is always given in PMII, this label can be used to complete other empty labels by retrieving the *institution* entity with API provided by OpenAlex³. If only one institution can be matched, then the empty labels can be completed based on the institutional information retrieved. If more than one institution can be matched, it means that several institutions share the same *display_name*. For example, Northwestern University may exist in many countries. In order to solve this problem, we looked deeper into the *display_name* labelled to each institution, and found that these institution names were actually unstandardized, such as “Department of Molecular Biosciences, Rice Institute for Biomedical Research, Northwestern University, Evanston, USA”. Then, string matching becomes a necessity, which will be used to match institution names on the one hand, and match country names and transform them to two-letter country codes on the other hand. By combining two aspects of information to search in OpenAlex, the problem can be solved.

According to the above solution, 55 pieces of institutional information (20.2%) can be completed, covering 25 articles. Those pieces that fail to be completed are on account of no corresponding institution entity can be retrieved with the API provided by OpenAlex. Possible reasons include the following:

- The institution types are special, such as virtual organizations, government departments and other unconventional scientific research institutions, which are not recognized by OpenAlex as entities with unique ids.
- The institution names are not standardized and hard to split, such as the *display_name* “Institute of Biophysics Chinese Academy of Sciences Beijing 100101 P. R. China”.

Analysis for CMII

Among 100 articles with CMII, 1,665 pieces of institutional information that is entirely empty are recognized. A possible way of information completion is to retrieve articles with the same author published in the same year, and use the institutional information in these articles to complete the articles with CMII. For example, an author A with an *author.id* A2246689996 published a journal article W with a *work.id* W2103017472 in 2000, but the institutional information is empty for A in W. If retrieving all articles authored by A published in 2000, we will find that A published two articles in 2000 in actual, and the other one labelled the institution named Stanford University for A. Then we may regard that A belonged to Stanford University when publishing W.

³ Missing-institutions we refer to is a phenomenon existing in journal articles. However, OpenAlex provides a list where the information of each institution indexed in the database as an entity is given. Therefore, we can complete the PMII by matching institution entities in the list.

It should be noted that in practice, it is possible that an author belongs to more than one institution at the same time or moves from one institution to another within a year. Given that the former might be relevant to short-term work or titling phenomenon, and the latter is somewhat not so common, our solution is to label the institution with the most frequency in all articles the author published in the same year. Another concern is that some authors might only have several articles, none of which is labelled with institutional information for these authors. Considering the complexity of data collection, the difficulty of authorship disambiguation, and the actual needs of research, the solution for these authors is not discussed in this study.

According to the above solution, 1,113 pieces of institutional information (66.8%) can be completed, covering 86 articles. Those pieces that fail to be completed are on account that the authors did not publish other articles in the same year or other articles did not label institutional information for the authors.

Using publishers' websites and Scopus as references to check the accuracy of 86 articles whose institutional information have been completed, we will find two cases – verifiable and non-verifiable. The verifiable case refers to that the institutional information can be learned from publishers' websites, full texts of articles or Scopus, which can be further divided into two situations:

- All authors' institutions are missing, because the algorithms developed by OpenAlex cannot extract institutional information from some publishers' websites where the position of institutional information and the page layouts are irregular. However, for such cases, Scopus usually manages to label the institutional information for each author in the articles.
- Only some authors' institutions are missing, but the reason is unknown. One possible reason is that something is wrong, like a network error when OpenAlex is crawling the data.

The non-verifiable case refers to that the institutional information cannot be learned from publishers' websites, full texts of articles or Scopus, which can be further divided into four situations:

- In group-author articles, some authors are represented by other authors, with prepositions such as “on behalf of”, or the authorship is an organization like an academic committee, whose members are specified but with no detailed information offered. For the former, representing authors are labelled with institutional information; for the latter, no one is labelled with institutional information.
- Due to the publication regulations, only corresponding authors are matched to their institutions. Institutional information of other authors is not provided.
- Types of works are mis-classified. For example, abstracts, without certain authors, are classified into the *journal article* type. In fact, the current *type* field of works in OpenAlex uses Crossref's “type” controlled vocabulary, which is considered not perfect enough and will be improved in the future according to the official statement from the platform (OpenAlex, 2022).
- Other reasons. For example, we have come across articles in OpenAlex, by authors who are not found in the author lists provided by the publishers. Or say, these “authors” are not the real authors of the articles. But the reason why these “authors” are labeled as authors of these articles is unknown to us.

Summary of causes and possible solutions to the missing-institutions

According to the exploration above, five major causes to the missing-institutions can be concluded – unstandardized institution names (including “splittable institution names” and

“non-splittable institution names”), group authorships, unstandardized authorship labelling, unstandardized document types and platform deficiencies (including “unincluded institution” and “platform functional deficiencies”), detailed in Figure 5.

Note: *Non-supplementable* in this study refers to that information cannot be completed with automatic methods based on the data from OpenAlex itself.

Figure 5. Causes for missing-institutions

In general, the missing data can be completed to some extent by procedural steps:

- For PMII, splittable institution names that are given in the label *display_name* can be used to retrieve the full information of institution entities from OpenAlex.
- For CMII, combined information of authors and publication years can be used to infer the institutional information. We have proposed a set of rules to make the completed information as accurate as possible. But whether this method is robust enough to be used in practice remains to be further confirmed.

However, the fact that a large part of the data is still difficult to supplement or verify reflects different types of problems during the publication process. The problems include the inconsistent format in which authors write their institution names, the inconsistent requirements of journals for labelling institutions, and the inconsistent standards for organising data and metadata on publishers’ websites etc. In addition, some special cases also deserve our attention. For example, most cases of “group authorships” do not present each author’s institution information. How to count and assign credits for the participating institutions of these publications remains a practical challenge.

Huge difference made by completing missing-institution data

In the previous section, possible solutions for PMII and CMII are proposed respectively. In this section, we will adopt the solution for PMII to complete part of the missing-institution data. The accuracy of information completed with this solution can be guaranteed without manual checking, because the institution matched by *display_name* is certain and the institutional information retrieved is based on the OpenAlex’s self-contained data. In this way, the distribution of journal articles before and after the data completion can be compared.

We have filled the empty labels of PMII in the 17,311 journal articles mentioned above to conduct a preliminary comparison. These articles cover 106,823 pieces of institutional

information, among which 66,510 pieces and 71,829 pieces have full information before and after the data completion respectively. Figure 6 demonstrates the distribution of countries among articles with FII and the number and growth rate of articles with FII corresponding to each country. It can be learned that the percentage of Chinese institutions has been obviously underestimated by using missing-institution data. Before completing the data, there are only 12,899 pieces of information of Chinese institutions, covering 3,003 articles. After completing the data, 15,166 (a growth rate of 17.58%) pieces of Chinese institutional information can be recognized, covering 3,202 articles. It means that if analysing on the country level, 199 (6.2%) articles affiliated with Chinese institutions will be neglected if directly using data provided by OpenAlex.

Figure 6. Distribution of countries among articles with FII and the number and growth rate of articles with FII corresponding to each country before and after the data completion

As the results above seem to show that completing the missing-institution data can really make a difference, a case study based on a published research will be conducted in the following part to further prove our finding.

In August, 2022, a study on the network effects of productivity and prominence among scientists was published in *Nature Communication* (Li et al., 2022), which used MAG as its data source. One of the indicators used to describe the network effects is the *institutional prestige*. Li et al.'s study has mentioned the serious problem of lacking institutional information in MAG, but chosen to directly exclude the articles with missing-institutions when analysing the data. Therefore, we intend to adopt the method in which their study used institutional information and the formula which was used to calculate the institutional prestige, and apply our solution to the completion of PMII described in the last section, so as to compare the results of the calculation of the institutional prestige before and after the data completion.

Li et al. (2022) used journal articles in the fields of biology, chemistry, mathematics, medicine and physics, and journal articles and conference proceedings in the field of computer science from 1950 to 2019 as the sample data. The institutional prestige of each institution for each year and each field was calculated, and the 10 institutions with the highest prestige are regarded as the elite institutions for a certain year in a specific field. Whether to be an elite institution is a 0-1 variable in the analysis of their study. Thereby, we selected journal articles published in 2019 in the field of mathematics as sample A to conduct the following comparative analysis.

The subsequent procedures are as follows:

- 1) Select all articles with FII in A as dataset B, and extract the list of all institutions covered by articles in B, represented as I . Let the total number of institutions be n^{inst} .

- 2) Sort the articles in B in the descending order according to the number of citations, and mark the articles ranking the upper 8th percentile as highly cited articles.
- 3) For each institution $i \in I$, count the number of highly cited articles in B in which there is an authorship belonging to i , represented as N_i^{high} . Record the average and the standard deviation of the N_i^{high} of all institutions as $\overline{N^{high}}$ and σ respectively.
- 4) According to the formula used in Li et al.'s study $p_i^{inst} = \frac{(N_i^{high} - \overline{N^{high}})}{\sigma/\sqrt{n^{inst}}}$, calculate the institutional prestige p_i^{inst} for each institution i . The institutional prestige ranking list L_1 and the elite institution list L_{E1} before the data completion can be received.
- 5) Based on our previous analysis, the PMII in articles in A can be partly completed to obtain a new dataset C of articles with FII. Repeat the last four steps, and the institutional prestige ranking list L_2 and the elite institution list L_{E2} after the data completion can be received.

By comparing the results before and after completing the missing-institution data, the following two aspects of differences can be identified.

Firstly, the values of the institutional prestige have witnessed an overall change. Focusing on institutions included in both L_1 and L_2 , the result of a paired samples t-test indicates a significant difference between the institutional prestige before and after the data completion.

Table 1. Result of the paired samples t-test

	Paired Differences	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
Pair	before-after	-0.766	16.292	0.108	-0.979	-0.554	-7.076	22629	.000

Secondly, the elite institution lists before and after completing the missing-institution data obviously vary from each other. Comparing the institutions included in L_{E1} and L_{E2} respectively, not only the institutional ranking has changed to a certain extent, but also the institutions included have become different. Whereas University of Electronic Science and Technology of China dropped from the 10th to the 14th place (out of the elite list), previously ranked 31st Harvard University entered the elite institution list after the data completion. Even for such two universities with significant disparity in academic standing, the result has been distorted, which can be very noticeable in the elite list with only 10 institutions. There will be a high risk of bias on the research results obtained from analysis based on the missing-institution data.

Table 2. Elite institution lists before and after the data completion

<i>Before the data completion</i>				<i>After the data completion</i>			
Rank	Institution name	Country	Institutional prestige	Rank	Institution name	Country	Institutional prestige
1	Tsinghua University	China	4540.04	1	Tsinghua University	China	4868.50
2	Huazhong University of Science and Technology	China	3436.47	2	University of Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	3621.90

3	University of Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	3436.47	3	Huazhong University of Science and Technology	China	3448.76
4	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	United States	3138.68	4	Stanford University	United States	3292.93
5	Nanyang Technological University	Singapore	3121.16	5	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	United States	3206.36
6	Stanford University	United States	3068.61	6	Nanyang Technological University	Singapore	3119.79
7	Southeast University	China	2963.51	7	Southeast University	China	3050.54
8	Harbin Institute of Technology	China	2945.99	8	Harbin Institute of Technology	China	2894.71
9	Hong Kong Polytechnic University	China	2823.38	9	Hong Kong Polytechnic University	China	2773.52
10	University of Electronic Science and Technology of China*	China	2648.21	10	Harvard University*	United States	2704.26

Note: * denotes institutions that enter or leave the elite institution list after the data completion.

From the above case study, we may find that visible distortion exists in the calculation of the institution prestige and the corresponding ranking before and after the data completion. If relevant practices like the institutional ranking are carried out on this basis, there is a high risk that results will be skewed. In fact, most current practices, such as Leiden Ranking (Waltman et al., 2012), do include scientific outputs in their measurements. Most of these practices tend to adopt those long-established authoritative data sources like WoS and Scopus to ensure the reliable results. However, as more and more open platforms become popular, it should be more careful when using missing-institution data, whether to conduct research based on institutional information, or to support relevant institutional ranking or evaluation practices.

Discussion

Underlying reasons for missing-institution data

Missing-institutions is a phenomenon caused by a variety of factors, which can be divided into two major categories as follows.

The first ones are factors that naturally exist and cannot be avoided, among which the publication year and the document type are two typical examples. During the early periods when the publishing process was not standardized enough, many articles were not labelled with sufficient institutional information. Our results do reveal that the phenomenon of missing-institutions happens more frequently in earlier years. Besides, document type is also a major cause. Not all types of works should be marked with authorships and their institutions. Although our focus is journal articles, the works of this type in OpenAlex are not restricted to research articles, but include types such as the abstract as well. Thereby, for some fields in Humanities, in which the major form of research outcomes is not research articles, missing-institutions might be more prevalent. On this basis, it seems to be more understandable that as shown in our results, the problem is more severe in *Notes and Queries*, a journal founded in 1849, which is one of the earliest academic journals published by Oxford, publishing notes, readers' Q&A and book

reviews on English language, literature and history. Maybe due to the age of the journal and the diversity of its document types, missing-institution data exist broadly in it.

The second ones are factors that are human-caused which could be possibly avoided. Among five main reasons we have found, missing-institutions caused by unstandardized institution names is mostly generated during the publication process, either because of authors' careless writing or due to editors' poor proofreading. Missing-institutions caused by group authorships might be credited to the non-uniformed standards on how to label and handle the institutional information in such articles. Missing-institutions caused by unstandardized labelling may be due to different regulations of different journals or publishers, some of which may not require authors to label the institutions other than the reprinting address when publishing. In terms of unstandardized document types, different from what we have mentioned in the first kind of factors, here it mainly refers to the inconsistent rules for defining document types in different databases. Furthermore, platform deficiencies like the neglect of some institutions of unconventional types or imperfect algorithm designs also lead to the missing-institutions. Therefore, it can be more explainable that missing-institutions is found more prevalent in articles published by publishers like Cambridge University Press, whose approach of labelling institutional information is not conventional. To be more specific, on these publishers' website pages, authors' name and their institutional information are not presented on the same interface. In other words, users need to click to access to the institutional information, which may be one of the reasons that weaken the effect of OpenAlex's data crawling algorithms. We also find that missing-institutions is common in some journals (e.g., *The Lancet*) published by Elsevier. This may be partly due to the phenomenon of group authors that is particularly prominent in some fields in life science and natural science.

Possible ways to better use missing-institution data

Since avoiding missing-institutions in research is hard, researchers need to find approaches to reduce the impact of the problem to the best of their abilities.

On the one hand, unavoidable factors that may affect the completeness of institutional information should be taken into full consideration when using the data. When selecting a sample to analyze, researchers should have a look at the coverage of needed data in different periods and set a suitable time span. Document type should also be restricted. Anyway, data limitations should be carefully checked and reported.

On the other hand, potentially avoidable factors should be overcome as far as possible by taking full advantage of multiple data source and relevant techniques. Researchers can choose subscription-based databases with more refined data processing as supplementary data sources to fit their needs. It should be noted that no database is perfect anyhow. Identifying the strength and weakness of each database is the prerequisite for combined use. Researchers can also try to complete the missing-institution data. Our study has explored two approaches to deal with PMII and CMII respectively, based on data from OpenAlex itself. Other techniques such as institution name disambiguation can be applied to standardize institution names as well.

As data users, there are some factors causing missing-institutions that can be avoided with a dedicate research design or combined use of data sources and techniques. However, the effect of factors like group authorships and unstandardized labeling cannot be relieved by our own effort, which calls for more stakeholders' joint efforts. Anyway, researchers should be fully aware of the data deficiency and carefully analyze the potential bias caused by missing information in practice, rather than simply ignoring the problems.

Fundamental solutions to data deficiency

In order to comprehensively solve the missing-institution problem and obtain institution data with higher quality, concerted effort from the whole academic community is needed (see Figure 7).

First of all, open science is a general trend that cannot be halted. Doing It Together science (DITOs) Consortium has developed a piece of policy brief to inform decision makers who have adopted Citizen Science or Open Science on the synergies between these approaches and the benefits of considering them together (DITOs Consortium, 2018). Given this background, open resources will become more and more widespread. As the demand for more comprehensive data is getting stronger and stronger, different stakeholders including open resource providers, maintainers and users should be more motivated to enhance the quality of the data.

Secondly, policies or regulations related to data generation and data use should be formulated and released to guide the practice. For example, the FAIR Data (data that are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) Action Plan was launched in 2018 to serve as a rubric for Member States and research communities to develop context-specific plans on how to implement FAIR data in their countries and/or research areas (Hodson et al., 2018). If more countries and regions can be covered by such guidance, the data quality might be improved more effectively.

Last but not least, different stakeholders' participation in the all-round management of the process from publication, digital publishing to database inclusion is the radical way to tackle the missing-institution problem. At the writing stage, authors' awareness of obeying academic regulations should be enhanced, which is a basic prerequisite for a healthy academic ecology. At the publishing stage, the labelling of institutional information needs to be standardized, which can make it more convenient for subsequent data integration and processing. When authors or publishers provide ambiguous data, it will be difficult for data aggregators to provide accurate data or at least statistically reliable one (Huang et al., 2014). At the developing and utilizing stage, data platforms should shoulder more responsibilities. WoS has set a good example for the standardization of institution names, who provides the enhanced field to integrate the preferred names and variants of each institution⁴, effectively improving the institutional information quality. Moreover, including more diverse types of institutions in the platform will provide users with richer and more comprehensive data, and crowdsourcing to complete the missing-institution data might be an effective approach for an open platform to better serve the relevant research and practice. In fact, some platforms like Research Organization Registry (ROR), registering open persistent identifiers for research organizations, and some projects like FREYA, aiming to extend the infrastructure for persistent identifiers, have been established to break down the barriers among different data sources to achieve a higher level of data correlation and harmonization. The problem is that the use of these platforms varies from country to country and from discipline to discipline, which calls for an urgent need to build a broader and more inclusive academic community.

⁴ Web of Science Core Collection Help:
https://images.webofknowledge.com/WOKRS535R52/help/WOS/hs_organizations_enhanced.html

Figure 7. Solutions to the phenomenon of missing-institutions

Conclusion

Based on the context of open science, our study has investigated the phenomenon of missing-institutions in OpenAlex, aiming to emphasize the severity of data deficiency by analyzing an outstanding data problem in this welcomed open data platform. Our results show that the missing-institution data is prevalent in OpenAlex, and journal articles with missing-institutions distribute more in earlier years, research fields like Art and History and certain journals and publishers. Then possible causes and solutions to the problem are given. We further use a case to unveil the potential distortion of research results by using missing-institution data. Finally, the underlying reasons and ways to tackle the problem are discussed.

Indeed, there are several limitations in our study. Firstly, missing information is just one of the manifestations of data quality issues. We will further investigate into the accuracy of the institutional information in OpenAlex in the later analysis. Secondly, the problem of data quality is not only present in the institutional information in OpenAlex, but also a common dilemma for all kinds of information on all data platforms to varying degrees. Our future studies will extend to comparisons among various open databases and more kinds of data quality issues. This study mainly focuses on institutional data provided by OpenAlex. Further issues like how to deal with the problem of name disambiguation to properly use the data we have retrieved will leave to future work.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (grant no. 71974150, 72004169).

References

- AlShebli, B. K., Rahwan, T., & Woon, W. L. (2018). The preeminence of ethnic diversity in scientific collaboration. *Nature Communications*, 9(1), 5163. doi:10.1038/s41467-018-07634-8
- Boulton, G. (2012). Open your minds and share your results. *Nature*, 486(7404), 441-441. doi:10.1038/486441a
- Chawla, D. S. (2022). Massive open index of scholarly papers launches [Press release]. Retrieved from <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-022-00138-y>
- DITOs Consortium (2018). Citizen Science & Open Science: Synergies & Future Areas of Work. Retrieved from <https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/10043574>
- Han, P., Shi, J., Li, X., et al. (2014). International collaboration in LIS: global trends and networks at the country and institution level. *Scientometrics*, 98(1), 53-72. doi:10.1007/s11192-013-1146-x
- Hodson, S., Jones, S., Collins, S., et al. (2018). FAIR Data Action Plan: Interim recommendations and actions from the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR data.
- Huang, S., Yang, B., Yan, S., et al. (2014). Institution name disambiguation for research assessment. *Scientometrics*, 99, 823-838. doi:10.1007/s11192-013-1214-2
- Li, W., Zhang, S., Zheng, Z., et al. (2022). Untangling the network effects of productivity and prominence among scientists. *Nature Communications*, 13(1), 4907. doi:10.1038/s41467-022-32604-6
- Mirowski, P. (2018). The future(s) of open science. *Social Studies of Science*, 48(2), 171-203. doi:10.1177/0306312718772086
- Molinari, J.-F., & Molinari, A. (2008). A new methodology for ranking scientific institutions. *Scientometrics*, 75(1), 163-174. doi:10.1007/s11192-007-1853-2
- OpenAlex. (2022). Work - OpenAlex documentation. Retrieved from <https://docs.openalex.org/about-the-data/work#type>
- Priem, J., Piwowar, H., & Orr, R. (2022). OpenAlex: A fully-open index of scholarly works, authors, venues, institutions, and concepts. *Arxiv*, abs/2205.01833.
- Scheidsteger, T., & Haunschild, R. (2022). Comparison of metadata with relevance for bibliometrics between Microsoft Academic Graph and OpenAlex until 2020. *Arxiv*, abs/2206.14168.
- Scheidsteger, T., Haunschild, R., Hug, S. E., et al. (2018). The concordance of field-normalized scores based on Web of Science and Microsoft Academic data: A case study in computer sciences. *Arxiv*, abs/1802.10141.
- Tang, X., Li, X., & Ma, F. (2022). Internationalizing AI: evolution and impact of distance factors. *Scientometrics*, 127(1), 181-205. doi:10.1007/s11192-021-04207-3
- UNESCO. (2021). *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. Retrieved from <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949.locale=en>
- Waltman, L., Calero Medina, C., Kosten, J., et al. (2012). The Leiden Ranking 2011/2012: Data collection, indicators, and interpretation. *CoRR*, abs/1202.3941. doi:10.1002/asi.22708
- Wang, D., Hu, L., Cheng, Q., et al. (2022). Inequality of authors' reference reuse. *Journal of Information Science*, 016555152211110. doi:10.1177/01655515221111062
- Woelfle, M., Olliaro, P., & Todd, M. H. (2011). Open science is a research accelerator. *Nature Chemistry*, 3(10), 745-748. doi:10.1038/nchem.1149
- Wolszczak-Derlacz, J., & Parteka, A. (2011). Efficiency of European public higher education institutions: a two-stage multicountry approach. *Scientometrics*, 89(3), 887-917. doi:10.1007/s11192-011-0484-9
- Zhao, Z., Bu, Y., & Li, J. (2021). Characterizing scientists leaving science before their time: Evidence from mathematics. *Information Processing & Management*, 58(5), 102661. doi:10.1016/j.ipm.2021.102661